

PROVINCES AND GOVERNORS IN THE ERA OF THE PROPHET (1-11 AH) (622-632 AD)

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Abstract

This paper has discussed a topic of utmost importance, shedding light on the initial steps taken towards the establishment of Islamic state during the era of prophethood, and the stages that the state went through from the migration of the Prophet (peace be upon him) until his death. The paper has also investigated the factors that influenced the geographical and political expansion of the state until its primary foundation was established, with all tribes and socio-political entities in the Arabian Peninsula declaring their allegiance to the state, either by embracing Islam or seeking protection as non-Muslim subjects (dhimmis). The paper has explored the stages through which Islam entered all the regions that formed the Islamic state, providing an overview of these regions, their inhabitants, and the religions of their people before the advent of Islam. It has documented examples of correspondence between the Prophet (peace be upon him) and the tribal leaders, inviting them to Islam and explaining its principles, and he promised to maintain their leadership positions if they responded positively to his invitation. Furthermore, the paper has presented profiles of the governors appointed by the Prophet (peace be upon him) and discusses the criteria for their selection. It has also presented examples of the recommendations and guidance that the Prophet (peace be upon him) provided to these governors. The study has concluded with several significant findings. Firstly, it has highlighted the enormous impact of the conquest of Makkah in the eighth year of the Hijra on the tribes' declaration of their acceptance of Islam. Some of the tribes embraced Islam out of genuine conviction, while others believed they could not resist the growing power of the Islamic state. Secondly, the paper also highlighted the criteria adopted by the Prophet (peace be upon him) in selecting governors, which confirmed that he did not appoint individuals who actively sought positions of power and governance.

Keywords: Era of Prophethood, Provinces, Governors, Regions, Embracing Islam.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of this topic lies in its focus on a significant aspect of the geographical formation of the Islamic state during the Prophetic era. It documents the integration of various regions under the state's authority, examines how the Prophet (peace be upon him) engaged with their inhabitants, and explores the strategies he employed in governing these territories.

Additionally, it highlights the governors appointed by the Prophet (peace be upon him), the criteria he used in their selection, and the guidance he provided to them to deal effectively with the inhabitants of the region.

The Prophet (peace be upon him) appointed a group of his companions to assist in managing the affairs of the emerging Islamic state. These assignments varied based on necessity.

Some examples include:

- Expedition Leaders who were mainly reconnaissance patrols.
- Scribes who were responsible for recording revelation and other official correspondences.
- Deputies whom the Prophet (peace be upon him) assigned to govern in his absence when he (peace be upon him) traveled outside al-Madinah.
- Ambassadors who were sent to deliver messages to kings and tribal leaders.
- Tax Collectors (Sā'āt) who were assigned to collect zakat, particularly from various tribes.

Furthermore, the Prophet (peace be upon him) appointed some of his companions for special assignments. For example,

- *Hudhayfah ibn al-Yaman* was Keeper of the Prophet's secrets.
- *Thabit ibn Qays* was the Prophet's orator.
- *Hassan ibn Thabit* was the Prophet's poet.
- Some companions served as his personal guards.
- *Zayd ibn Thabit* was the Prophet's translator.
- *Bilal ibn Rabah* was the Prophet's treasurer and muezzin (caller to prayer).

Notably, these appointees did not receive salaries, nor were their positions permanent. Their roles were task-specific, and once completed, they would return to their original professions —merchants would go to their trade, farmers to their agriculture, artisans to their craftsmanship, and herders to managing their livestock. The study has adopted a descriptive historical and inductive methodology to answer the following pertinent questions, which the extant literature has remained silent to examine. When did the political and geographical map of the Islamic state take shape during the Prophetic era? What were the key factors that influenced this formation? How were the regions that became part of the state administered? What criteria did the Prophet (peace be upon him) follow in selecting governors? The study is confined to the period starting from the Prophet's (peace be upon him) migration to al-Madinah al-Munawwarah and his settlement there on 8 Rabi' al-Awwal, 1 AH (September 23, 622 CE). Geographically, the research focuses specifically on al-Madinah as the state's capital, along with al-Makkah, Ta'if, Yemen, Oman, and Bahrain as the major provinces under the Islamic state. Furthermore, the study examines the governors appointed by the Prophet (peace be upon him), rather than the tax collectors (sā'āt) who were sent to collect zakat from various tribes at their settlements and water sources. Therefore, the study is structured into the following 7 main sections including the introduction. The subsequent section 2 introduces Yathrib (al-Madinah), the Capital of Islamic State. Section 3 discusses the provinces of al-Makkah and Ta'if during the Prophetic Era, followed by a discussion on the Province of Yemen during the Prophetic Era in section 4. The next section 5 focuses on the Provinces of Bahrain and section 6 discusses Oman during the Prophetic Era. The final section 7 concludes the study.

2. THE CAPITAL OF THE ISLAMIC STATE DURING THE PROPHETIC ERA: AL-MADINAH

2.1. Names of Al-Madinah

Al-Madina has several names, which include:

Yathrib: This was the city's name before the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) settled there. It was called Yathrib because the first person to inhabit it was Yathrib bin Qaniah bin Iram, a

descendant of Sam, the son of Noah (peace be upon him). The Prophet (peace be upon him) disliked this name because it carried negative meanings such as corruption, expulsion, abandonment, and blame¹. The name Yathrib appears in the Quran in the following verse:

"And 'remember' when a faction of them said, 'O people of Yathrib, there is no point in you staying[here]'². When the Prophet (peace be upon him) arrived and settled in the city, he renamed it "Al-Madinah"³. Other names of al-Madinah in the Quran includes dwellings, "And those who had settled in the dwellings (al-Madinah) and 'embraced' the faith before 'the arrival of' the emigrants, they love whoever immigrates to them"⁴.

In addition to Al-Madinah, the city has been known by several other names, including *Tayyibah* (pure and pleasant), *Tabah* (another form of purity and goodness), *Al-'Adhraa* (virgin, indicating its purity), *Jaabirah* (the healer), *al-Majboorah* (the comforted), *al-Muhabbah* (the Loving (City)), *al-Mahboobah* (the beloved (City)), and *al-Qasimah* (the Divider or The Just).⁵

2.2. The Demographic and Social Composition of Yathrib at the Time of the Prophet's Migration

When the Prophet (peace be upon him) arrived in Yathrib as a migrant, its population comprised various groups. The Jewish tribes included Banu Qurayza, Banu Qaynuqa, and Banu Nadir⁶. The Arab inhabitants consisted of the Aws and Khazraj tribes, along with some smaller mixed Arab groups. Furthermore, there was a small Christian community in the city⁷.

2.3. Pre-Islam Religious Life in Yathrib

The main religions present in Yathrib at the time of the Prophet's (peace be upon him) migration were paganism, along with some followers of the Jewish and Christian faiths. Furthermore, some members of the Aws and Khazraj had already embraced Islam before the migration⁸.

2.4. The Initial Establishment of the Prophet (peace be upon him) in Al-Madinah

One of the first actions of the Prophet (peace be upon him) in al-Madinah was the construction of Masjid Quba, the first mosque built in Islam. Quba is located at the southwestern entrance of al-Madinah and was the first area the Prophet (peace be upon him) reached upon his migration. He stayed among Banu Amr ibn Awf⁹ and resided at the house of Kulthum ibn al-Hadm¹⁰. This occurred on Monday morning, 8th Rabi' al-Awwal, in the 14th year of Prophethood, which corresponds to September 23, 622 CE, marking the first year of Hijrah¹¹. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) stayed there for a few days and established Masjid Quba on the site of a Mirbad¹² belonging to Kulthum ibn al-Hadm. It was the first mosque founded upon piety¹³.

2.5. The Arrival of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) in Yathrib

On Friday morning, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) set out for al-Madinah. When the time for Dhuhr prayer came, he stopped and prayed Jumu'ah with Banu Salim ibn 'Awf in the Valley of al-Raanoonaa¹⁴. Then, he continued his journey northward, passing by different clans of the Ansar, each of whom eagerly wished to host him. However, the Prophet (peace be upon him) told them, "Leave it, for it is commanded", referring to his she-camel. By the will of Allah, the she-camel knelt down in the neighborhood of Banu Najjar, the clan of his grandfather 'Abd al-Muttalib's maternal relatives. Abu Ayyub al-Ansari immediately rushed to take the Prophet's belongings and carried them into his house. The Ansar continued requesting that the Prophet (peace be upon him) stay with them, but he responded: "A man stays where his belongings are"¹⁵.

According to a narration by Anas ibn Malik, the Prophet's servant, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) asked, "Which of our family's houses is the closest?" Abu Ayyub replied, "I am, O Messenger

of Allah! This is my house, and this is my door." The Prophet (peace be upon him) then said, "Then go and prepare a resting place for us." Abu Ayyub responded, "Come in, upon the blessings of Allah!"¹⁶.

2.6. Steps taken by the Prophet (peace be upon him) to Establish the State in al-Madinah

- 1. Building the Mosque:** It was a place for prayers, where Muslims met and formed bonds. The Prophet (peace be upon him) received delegations there. It served as the headquarters for his envoys and diplomatic missions, military expeditions, and it also became a shelter for homeless Muhajirin (migrants).
- 2. Providing Housing for the Muhajirin:** The Prophet (peace be upon him) allocated land to the Muhajirin. Some lands had no owners, while others were generously donated by the Ansar. This ensured the settlement and stability of the migrants, giving them a new homeland.
- 3. Establishing Mu'aakhah (Brotherhood) between the Muhajirin and the Ansar:** The Ansar welcomed the Muhajirin with open hearts and homes. They prioritized the needs of the migrants over their own. The Muhajirin initially felt uneasy receiving so much generosity and also felt like strangers in a new land. The system of Mu'aakhah was a practical solution to the psychological challenges of the Muhajirin, making them feel at home among their brothers and family members.
- 4. Writing the Constitution of al-Madinah:** The Prophet (peace be upon him) drafted a formal document known as "*al-Madinah Charter*" or "*The Book*", as referred to by some sources. This document organized relations between the various groups in al-Madinah. It defined the rights and responsibilities of all inhabitants. It established a central authority in the city. It criminalized alliances with enemies of the new state.
- 5.** The Prophet (peace be upon him) signed treaties with surrounding tribes. These treaties made them neutral in the conflict between him and the Quraysh.

3. THE PROVINCES OF AL-MAKKAH AND Ta'if AND THEIR GOVERNORS IN THE PROPHETIC ERA

3.1. The Province of al-Makkah and Its Governors

History of al-Makkah

The history of al-Makkah revolves around the House (Ka'ba), which Allah the Almighty made a place of return for people and a sanctuary for those who seek security. He made it the Qiblah (direction of prayer) for monotheists from the time of Adam until the Day of Judgment. Allah the Almighty says:

*"Indeed, the first House [of worship] established for mankind was that at Bakkah – blessed and a guidance for the worlds. In it are clear signs [such as] the standing place of Abraham. And whoever enters it shall be safe. And [due] to Allah from the people is a pilgrimage to the House – for whoever is able to find thereto a way. But whoever disbelieves – then indeed, Allah is free from need of the worlds."*¹⁷ (Quran 3:96-97)

The Ka'ba was rebuilt multiple times. Some narrations suggest that the first to build it were the angels, while others say it was Adam (peace be upon him)¹⁸. However, the confirmed construction is that of Prophet Ibrahim (peace be upon him), as mentioned in the Quran. Allah the Almighty says: "*And [mention] when Abraham was raising the foundations of the House and [with him] Ismael, [they say], 'Our Lord, accept [this] from us. Indeed, you are the Hearing, the Knowing.'*"¹⁹

It is also said that the first to build the House was Prophet Ibrahim (peace be upon him). Later, it was destroyed and rebuilt by the Jurhum tribe and then rebuilt again by the Amalekites. Again, it was destroyed and then rebuilt by the Quraysh²⁰, the construction in which the Prophet Muhammad

(peace be upon him) participated before his Prophethood. This narration is authentically established in the Prophetic tradition, and at the time, he was thirty-five years old²¹.

3.2. The Location and Names of al-Makkah

Al-Makkah is situated in the western part of the Arabian Peninsula, in a narrow and elongated valley among the mountains of al-Sarah. It is an arid, barren land, surrounded on all sides by mountains, barren hills, and solid rocks, forming a natural enclosure around al-Makkah and its sacred Ka'ba²².

Various names for al-Makkah have been mentioned in the Quran, geographical books, and historical records. The most well-known names include al-Makkah²³, as mentioned in the Quran; *Bakkah*²⁴, also found in the Quran; *Al-Balad Al-Ameen*²⁵ (the secure city), *Umm Al-Qura*²⁶ (the mother of cities); *Ma'aad*²⁷; *Al-Haram*²⁸ (the sanctuary); and *Al-Bayt Al-'Atiq*²⁹ (the ancient house). Additionally, in the Torah, al-Makkah is referred to as *Faaraan*³⁰.

3.3. The Demographic and Social Composition of Al-Makkah

It is said that the Amalekites were among the first inhabitants of al-Makkah. They were followed by the Jurhum tribe from Yemen, who took in Ismael (peace be upon him), raising him in their midst and teaching him the Arabic language. However, the tyranny of the Jurhum tribe in al-Makkah led to their expulsion by the Banu Ghubshaan of the Khuza'ah tribe, who subsequently took control of al-Makkah and ruled it for approximately 300 years.

Later, the rule of al-Makkah passed from the Khuza'ah tribe to the Kinanah tribe, and then to Quraysh, a branch of Kinanah that traced its lineage to al-Nadr ibn Kinanah. The leadership of al-Makkah was consolidated under Qusayy ibn Kilaab, the fourth great-grandfather of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). Qusayy implemented several reforms, including the construction of Dar al-Nadwah, a meeting place for Quraysh leaders. Before his death, Qusayy divided the responsibilities of Ka'ba among his four sons. His son, 'Abd Manaaf ibn Qusayy, the third great-grandfather of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), was entrusted with providing water (Siqaayah) and provisions (Rifaadah) to pilgrims, as well as leading (Qiyaadah) the Quraysh.

After 'Abd Manaaf's death, his son, Haashim ibn 'Abd Manaaf, took charge of leading the Quraysh. Following Haashim's death, 'Abd al-Muttalib ibn Haashim assumed leadership and became responsible for the Ka'ba's water supply (Siqaayah). One of his significant achievements was re-digging the Zamzam well³¹.

3.4. Religious Life in Al-Makkah Before Islam

The original faith of al-Makkah's inhabitants was monotheism. According to historical accounts, the descendants of Adam (peace be upon him) settled in al-Makkah, but over time, religious practices changed. Monotheism was later revived when Allah sent Ismael (peace be upon him) to the Jurhum tribe³² with the teachings of Ibrahim (peace be upon him). Allah says in the Quran: "*And mention in the Book [the story of] Ismael. Indeed, he was true to his promise, and he was a messenger and a prophet*"³³.

The first person to introduce idol worship in al-Makkah was Amr ibn al-Hayy, the chief of the Khuza'ah tribe³⁴. Despite idol worship being the dominant religion in al-Makkah, spreading across the Arabian Peninsula through tradition and imitation, some individuals remained steadfast in the monotheistic faith of Ibrahim (peace be upon him). These people were known as the *Hunafa*, meaning "those who turned away" from idol worship.

3.5. Al-Makkah and It's Entry into Islam

Al-Makkah was liberated by the Muslims after 21 years of Quraysh's resistance to Islam. This resistance took many forms, including torture, persecution, murder, economic boycotts, ridicule, and propaganda against Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and his followers. After Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) migrated to al-Madinah, the Quraysh continued their hostility. They even wrote to Abdullah ibn Ubayy³⁵, saying: *"You have given shelter to our man (i.e., Muhammad). By Allah, either you fight him or expel him, or we will march against you with all our forces until we kill your warriors and take your women as captives"*³⁶. Furthermore, the Quraysh incited the Jews of al-Madinah against the Muslims after the Battle of Badr. They also engaged in several major battles against the Muslims, including the Battle of Badr, the Battle of Uhud, and the Battle of the Trench. These hostilities eventually ended temporarily with the Treaty of Hudaibiyyah, but the Quraysh violated the agreement. This led to the conquest of Al-Makkah in the 8th year of Hijrah, marking the city's full acceptance of Islam.

3.6. The Governor of Al-Makkah During the Prophetic Era

'Attab ibn Asid, also known as Abu 'Abd al-Rahman or Abu Muhammad (d.13 AH/634 CE)³⁷, embraced Islam on the day of the conquest when he was only 20 years old. Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) appointed him as the governor of al-Makkah when the Prophet (peace be upon him) left for the Battle of Hunayn against the Hawazin and Thaqif tribes who assembled to fight the Messenger (peace be upon him) under the leadership of Malik ibn Awf al-Nasri³⁸. 'Attab ibn Asid remained in his position as the governor of al-Makkah until the death of the Messenger (peace be upon him). 'Attab led the people in Hajj in the year of the conquest. His appointment was alongside Mu'adh ibn Jabal and Abu Musa al-Ash'ari to teach the people of al-Makkah about the Sunnah and Fiqh³⁹. The Messenger (peace be upon him) granted him a salary of one dirham per day. This was the first fixed salary for an official at the time of the Messenger (peace be upon him). 'Attab ibn Asid used to say this about the salary: *"Oh people! May Allah starve the stomach of whoever goes hungry for a dirham! The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) has granted me one dirham per day, and I have no need for anyone else"*⁴⁰.

Some accounts suggest that when the Prophet (peace be upon him) first left for Ta'if, he had appointed Hubayrah ibn Shibl al-Thaqafi⁴¹ as the governor of al-Makkah. However, upon his return, he officially installed 'Attab ibn Asid as the permanent governor. 'Attab was also the first to lead the people of al-Makkah in prayer after the Prophet (peace be upon him). Assuming that these accounts are true, his governorship did not last long, because when the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) wanted to return to al-Madinah, he appointed 'Attab ibn Asid as the governor of al-Makkah and left with him Abu Musa al-Ash'ari and Mu'adh ibn Jabal to educate the people Islam⁴².

3.7. 'Attab ibn Asid as an Administrator

Attab ibn Asid was known for his piety and asceticism⁴³. He was the first appointed governor of al-Makkah and also the first to lead the Hajj⁴⁴ as an official Amir after the conquest of al-Makkah.

Some historical reports suggest that 'Attab also served as a judge (Qadi) while being governor. He would write to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) regarding complex legal matters. One such case was when he sought clarification from the Prophet (peace be upon him) on the ruling concerning pre-Islamic usury (Riba) on debts incurred before people embraced Islam⁴⁵.

3.8. Advice of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) to 'Attab

When the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) appointed 'Attab as the governor of Mecca, he addressed him, saying, *"Do you know over whom I have appointed you?"* 'Attab replied, *"Allah and His Messenger know best."* The Prophet (peace be upon him) then said: *"I have appointed you over the*

people of Allah”⁴⁶. The Prophet (peace be upon him) also instructed ‘Attab to renew the boundary of the Al-Haram (Sacred Sanctuary) and to prohibit certain types of commercial transactions that were common in al-Makkah’s trading society. He specifically told him: “Two conditions in a sale are not permissible, nor a sale combined with a loan, nor the sale of what one does not possess, nor the consumption of profit from what is not in one’s ownership”⁴⁷.

It is said that ‘Attab passed away two years after the Prophet (peace be upon him)⁴⁸. Some accounts mention that his death coincided with the news of Abu Bakr Al-Siddiq’s (RA) passing from al-Madinah⁴⁹. Ibn Abd al-Barr suggests that he died around the same time as Abu Bakr (RA)⁵⁰.

3.9. The Province of al-Taa’if During the Prophetic Era

The city of al-Taa’if is located in the western part of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and is administratively affiliated with the Emirate of al-Makkah. It lies approximately 75 kilometers from al-Makkah and is surrounded by mountains from all directions. The city is well known for its orchards, grapes, roses, flowers, and perfumes⁵¹.

3.10. Names of al-Taa’if

The following are the names of al-Taa’if. Firstly, the ancient name of al-Taa’if was *Wajj* (وَجِّ) ⁵², named after *Wajj ibn ‘Abd al-Hayy*, one of the descendants of the ancient tribe of ‘Amaaleeq. The name *Wajj* also refers to the valley of al-Taa’if, which passes by the city from the southwest, then south, and finally to the east⁵³. Secondly, it is referred to as al-Taa’if. Due to its abundant agricultural production, al-Taa’if became a target for Bedouin tribes of the surrounding deserts. Therefore, the tribe of Thaqeef constructed a protective wall and a fortified structure around the city made from stone and clay, encompassing it from all sides⁵⁴. Thirdly, al-Taa’if is also referred to in the Qur’an as “the village”, as mentioned in the verse: “And they said, ‘Why was this Qur’an not sent down upon a great man from one of the two villages?’”⁵⁵ Ibn Abbas (RA) who is buried in al-Taa’if interpreted “the two villages” as referring to al-Makkah and al-Taa’if⁵⁶.

3.11. Demographic and Social Structure of al-Taa’if

One of the most prominent tribes that settled in al-Taa’if is the Thaqeef tribe, which remains one of the largest and most dominant tribes in the region to this day. Al-Taa’if was home to one of the most significant and renowned markets in pre-Islamic Arabia, which was the ‘Ukaz Market⁵⁷. In the pre-Islamic era, ‘Ukaz Market was not just a trading hub but also a cultural and social forum for various kinds of activities. It gathered Arab tribes for an entire month every year⁵⁸. The Prophet (peace be upon him) visited this market before Islam⁵⁹ and continued to frequent it after he started preaching. During the Makkan period of his mission, he actively invited the visiting Arab tribes to Islam at this marketplace.

3.12. Religions in al-Taa’if

The only religion practiced by the people of al-Taa’if before Islam was idolatry. They worshiped idols, and one of their most famous deities was *al-Laat*⁶⁰, which was a stone upon which they built a temple. It had caretakers from the Thaqeef tribe, and it was venerated by the Quraysh as well as many other Arab tribes. Allah says in the Qur’an, “Have you considered *al-Laat* and *al-‘Uzza*, and *Manaat*, the third—the other?” (Surah An-Najm: 19-20). After the people of al-Taa’if embraced Islam, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent *al-Mugheerah ibn Shu‘bah* to demolish it⁶¹.

3.13. The Stance of the People of al-Taa’if Toward Islam

The reaction of the people of al-Taa’if toward Islam was similar to that of the Quraysh leadership. In the tenth year of prophethood, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) traveled to al-Taa’if

seeking either support or protection, but instead, they rejected him, expelled him, and subjected him to harm. After the conquest of al-Makkah in the eighth year of Hijrah, and as its people embraced Islam, the tribes of Hawazin and Thaqeef allied against the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), attempting to resist the spread of Islam. This led to the famous Battle of Hunayn⁶² in Shawwal, 8 AH, where the coalition was decisively defeated. The Thaqeef tribe retreated to their fortresses in al-Taa'if, and the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) laid siege to the city for about twenty days. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) introduced new warfare techniques, such as the catapult (Manjaniq)⁶³ and the battering ram (Dabbabah).⁶⁴ However, after twenty days of unsuccessful attempts to breach the fortress, he ordered the siege to be lifted, stating, *"We have not been commanded to conquer al-Taa'if at this time"*⁶⁵. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) then made a compassionate proclamation, *"Any slave who leaves al-Taa'if and joins the Muslims will be freed"*. More than ten enslaved individuals took this offer⁶⁶, embraced Islam, and were freed by the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him). Owing to the mercy of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), after lifting the siege, instead of cursing the people of al-Taa'if, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) prayed for their guidance, saying, *"O Allah, guide the tribe of Thaqeef and bring them to Islam"*⁶⁷.

After the Battle of Tabuk, a delegation from the Thaqeef tribe approached the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), but only 'Urwah ibn Mas'ud al-Thaqafi accepted Islam. When 'Urwah returned to al-Taa'if to preach Islam, his own people killed him⁶⁸. In Ramadan of the same year, a second delegation from al-Taa'if visited the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), expressing their conditions for embracing Islam. Their demands included permission to commit adultery, to continue engaging in riba (usury), and to continue drinking alcohol. However, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) firmly rejected these requests, explaining that these acts were prohibited in Islam. After further discussions, the delegation accepted Islam, and the people of al-Taa'if finally entered the fold of Islam⁶⁹.

3.14. The Governor of al-Taa'if: 'Uthman ibn Abi al-'Aas (18 BH to 51 AH)⁷⁰

'Uthman ibn Abi al-'Aas ibn Bishr ibn 'Abd ibn Dahmaan al-Thaqafi⁷¹ was a noble, trustworthy leader, known by his family name Abu 'Abd Allah al-Thaqafi, al-Taa'ifi⁷². He embraced Islam secretly before the delegation of his tribe publicly declared their conversion. He frequently visited Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) to learn the Quran. He used to go to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) to learn the Qur'an from him, and if he found him asleep, he would go to Abu Bakr al-Siddiq, and some say he would go to Ubayy ibn Ka'ab to learn the Qur'an and Islam from them. The Prophet (peace be upon him) admired him and loved him for his eagerness to learn⁷³. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) appointed him as the governor of al-Taa'if, and both Abu Bakr and 'Umar later reaffirmed him in his position. 'Umar also appointed him over Oman and Bahrain. He was the one who prevented the tribe of Thaqeef from apostatizing, addressing them by saying, *"You were the last people to enter Islam, so do not be the first to leave it"*⁷⁴.

3.15. Advice of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) to 'Uthman

The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) assigned 'Uthman to lead the people in prayer, and he advised him to take their conditions into consideration, saying, *"O 'Uthman, lead the prayer but be considerate of the weakest among them, for among them are the elderly, the young, the weak, and those with needs"*⁷⁵. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) also instructed 'Uthman to build a mosque in the place where the idol of al-Taa'if was once worshipped⁷⁶. 'Uthman remained governor of al-Taa'if until the caliphate of 'Umar ibn al-Khattab (RA)⁷⁷.

4. YEMEN AND ITS GOVERNORS DURING THE PROPHETIC ERA

4.1. Introduction to Yemen⁷⁸

Yemen has several names, such as "The Green Yemen" (Al-Yaman Al-Khadra')⁷⁹, and the Romans referred to it as "Happy Arabia" (Arabia Felix)⁸⁰. Yemen is a vast and well-known land, though geographers have differed in defining its exact borders⁸¹. It is home to some of the oldest Arab civilizations, beginning with the al-Ma'iniyyat state, followed by Qataban, Hadramawt, and Himyar. Among the most famous of these states is the Kingdom of Saba' (Sheba), which is mentioned in the Qur'an, "Indeed, there was for [the tribe of] Saba' in their dwelling place a sign: two gardens on the right and on the left. [They were told], Eat from the provisions of your Lord and be grateful to Him. A good land [have you], and a forgiving Lord"⁸². One of its most famous rulers was Queen Bilqis (the Queen of Sheba), who accepted Islam after meeting Prophet Suleiman (peace be upon him) and said, "Indeed, I have wronged myself, and I submit with Suleiman to Allah, the Lord of the worlds"⁸³.

Yemen was known for its early script called "Musnad"⁸⁴, one of the oldest alphabets in the world. It faced foreign invasions from the Abyssinians and the Persians, and even the Romans attempted to conquer it.

4.2. Geographical Location and Population

Yemen is located in the southwestern corner of the Arabian Peninsula. It overlooks the Red Sea and commands a strategic position over the Bab al-Mandab Strait. Its unique and strategic location has long made it a target for foreign powers and ambitions. The exact beginning of ancient Yemeni history is unknown, but historians state that the earliest known inhabitants of Yemen were the descendants of Qahtan, who are referred to as the "Qahtani Arabs." They spread throughout much of the Arab world and established kingdoms in regions such as the Levant (Sham), Iraq, Oman, and al-Madinah. For this reason, they are considered the original Arabs, also referred to as the "pure Arabs" (al-'Arab al-'Aribah)⁸⁵.

4.3. History of Islam in Yemen

After three years of secret preaching, during which the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) selectively called those close to righteousness, he publicly declared his message from the heights of Mount Safa, following God's command, "So proclaim what you have been commanded, and turn away from the polytheists"⁸⁶. Due to the strong connections the people of Yemen and other Arab tribes had with the people of al-Makkah, the echoes of this new message quickly spread across the Arabian Peninsula and eventually reached them as well.

The spread of Islam in Yemen went through two main phases. The first phase focused on converting some influential individuals to Islam⁸⁷. They included Zayd ibn Harithah, the adopted son of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him)⁸⁸, the family of Yasir, who belonged to the Yemeni tribe of Madh'hij⁸⁹, Qays ibn Malik al-Arahbi⁹⁰, Dhu'ayb ibn Kulayb al-Khawlani⁹¹, and Abu Musa al-Ash'ari Abdullah ibn Qays⁹². These individuals, among others, played a significant role in encouraging the people of Yemen, as groups and individuals, to embrace Islam willingly and wholeheartedly.

The second phase began in the sixth year after the Treaty of Hudaibiyyah and continued until the Year of Delegations ('Aam al-Wufud). During this time, several Yemeni tribes began sending letters to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) declaring their acceptance of Islam. According to Ibn Ishaq, "The kings of Himyar and their envoys came to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) with a letter declaring their Islam upon his return from Tabuk"⁹³. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) responded to them with written messages confirming their rulership and explaining to them the

obligations of Zakat, including its categories and recipients, and the payment of jizyah for those among the People of the Book who chose to remain on their faith⁹⁴.

4.4. Governors of Yemen During the Prophetic Era

There is some confusion in certain sources regarding the officials appointed by the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) to govern Yemen. These sources often do not distinguish between governors who were permanent in their job and those temporarily assigned for specific missions, and would relinquish the post after completing the task. These include collectors of Zakat, preachers, among other tasks. For example, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent al-Muhajir ibn Abi Umayyah to Ṣan'a', and Ziyad ibn Labid al-Anṣari, among others. Meanwhile the following were governors whose terms were permanent:

4.5. Baadhaan⁹⁵ Baadhaan ibn Saasaan ibn Balaash

Some sources traced his lineage back to some Persian kings. He was the first non-Arab king to embrace Islam, and the first official governor in Islam appointed to Yemen⁹⁶. Baadhaan had been the governor of Yemen under the authority of the Persian emperor prior to embracing Islam⁹⁷. After his conversion, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) confirmed him in his position as governor. The reason for his acceptance of Islam was that the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent him a verbal message inviting him to Islam and promising that if he embraced the faith, he would be allowed to retain his governorship⁹⁸.

Some sources indicate that the correspondence between the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) and Baadhaan took place in the 7th year of Hijrah, while others suggest that he embraced Islam in the 10th year⁹⁹. We are of the opinion that his conversion and appointment took place in the 10th year of Hijrah, since most of the sources that mentioned him agree that he passed away shortly after his acceptance of Islam¹⁰⁰. Upon his conversion, all the Persians in Yemen who were under his leadership also embraced Islam, and he sent a delegation to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) to declare their acceptance of Islam. His governorship extended over all of Yemen, but it did not last long after his appointment, as he passed away—may Allah have mercy on him—in the 10th year of Hijrah. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) then appointed his son, Shahr ibn Baadhaan, as governor over Ṣan'a' and its surrounding regions¹⁰¹. However, he was killed by al-Aswad al-'Ansi¹⁰² before the death of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him).

4.6. Mu'adh ibn Jabal (20 BH – 18 AH / 603 – 639 CE)¹⁰³

He was Mu'adh ibn 'Amr al-Khazraji al-Anṣari, and he embraced Islam at the age of eighteen at the hands of Muṣ'ab ibn 'Umayr, the Messenger of Allah's (peace be upon him) envoy and missionary to the people of al-Madinah before the Hijrah¹⁰⁴. Mu'adh was a memorizer of the Qur'an, a jurist, pious, and very close to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him).

Appointment of Mu'adh over Mikhlaf al-Jund¹⁰⁵

After the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) returned from the Expedition of Tabuk, he received letters from the leaders of Yemen declaring their acceptance of Islam. In response, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent Mu'adh ibn Jabal and Abu Musa al-Ash'ari to Yemen, each assigned to Mikhlaf¹⁰⁶. He (peace be upon him) instructed them to, "Cooperate with each other, make things easy and do not make them difficult, give glad tidings and do not repel people"¹⁰⁷.

Mu'adh was assigned to work among the Ḥimyar tribe¹⁰⁸. He remained in his post until the death of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him)¹⁰⁹. The Prophet (peace be upon him) had instructed him to collect Zakat from the wealthy among the people of Yemen and to distribute it among their poor, without sending any portion of it back to the Messenger of Allah's (peace be upon him)¹¹⁰. His

governorship lasted fourteen months¹¹¹. After the death of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), Mu'adh returned during the caliphate of Abu Bakr al-Şiddiq, and then went out to join the military campaigns in al-Sham. When Abu 'Ubaydah ibn al-Jarrah fell ill, he appointed Mu'adh as his successor to lead the Muslim armies in al-Sham. 'Umar ibn al-Khaţţab confirmed him in that role, but Mu'adh passed away in the same year known in Islamic history as the year of 'Amwas (plague)¹¹² in 18 AH, a devastating outbreak that witnessed the martyr of thousands of the companions (RA).

4.7. Abu Musa al-Ash'ari¹¹³

'Abdullah ibn Qays ibn Sulaym ibn Ḥaḍar ibn Ḥarb ibn al-Ash'ari¹¹⁴ came to al-Makkah and entered into an alliance with Sa'id ibn al-'Aaş ibn Umayyah¹¹⁵. He embraced Islam in al-Makkah at the early stage of the Messenger of Allah's (peace be upon him) call. There are variations of opinions regarding where he settled after his conversion. Some sources state that he returned to his people to invite them to Islam. However, Ibn Ishaq, in his *Sirah*, mentions that he migrated to Abyssinia (al-Habasha) and remained there until the seventh year after Hijrah, when he arrived with the migrants (Muhajirin) aboard the ship while the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) was at Khaybar¹¹⁶. On the other hand, Ibn 'Abd al-Barr opined that he did not migrate to Abyssinia, but that his arrival coincided with the arrival of the ship carrying Ja'far ibn Abi Talib and his companions¹¹⁷. Abu Musa al-Ash'ari was highly skilled in reciting the Qur'an with proper tajwid. He was a knowledgeable jurist (faqih) and took part in several military expeditions during the lifetime of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him). He was also an exceptional military commander; under whose leadership many regions were opened (liberated) to Islam¹¹⁸. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) appointed Abu Musa al-Ash'ari as governor over Zabid, Aden, and other coastal regions of Yemen¹¹⁹. His appointment took place in the ninth year after Hijrah, following the return of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) from the Expedition of Tabuk. He also attended the Farewell Pilgrimage (Hijjat al-Wada') with the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) and then returned to Yemen¹²⁰. After the death of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), Abu Musa al-Ash'ari came to al-Madinah and later joined the Muslim conquests in the Levant (Sham). There is a disagreement regarding the year and place of Abu Musa's death. Some sources state that he passed away in Kufah, while others say it was in al-Makkah. As for the year of his death, it is variously reported as: 42 AH, 44 AH, 50 AH, or 52 AH¹²¹.

5. BAHRAIN AND ITS GOVERNORS DURING THE PROPHETIC ERA

5.1. Geographical Location

The island of Bahrain is located in Asia, off the eastern coast of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the Arabian Gulf. Before the advent of Islam, Bahrain was known by several names, including Dilmun, Tylos, and Awaal¹²².

5.2. Islam of the People of Bahrain

The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent Al-'Alaa' ibn al-Ḥaḍrami (d. 21 AH / 635 CE) with a letter to Al-Mundhir ibn Sawa (d. 11 AH / 633 CE), the ruler of Bahrain, inviting him and his people to Islam. This took place in the month of Rajab in the ninth year of Hijrah¹²³. However, Ibn Sa'ad recorded the date of this message as being after the return of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) from al-Ji'rana, following the siege of al-Taa'if in the eighth year after Hijrah¹²⁴.

The letter sent by the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) to Al-Mundhir had the following message:

*"Whoever performs our prayer, faces our Qiblah, and eats from what we slaughter, then he is a Muslim—he has the protection of Allah and the protection of His Messenger. Whoever among the Magians (Zoroastrians) desires this is safe; and whoever refuses must pay the jizyah (tribute)"*¹²⁵.

Al-Mundhir responded to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) informing him of the reaction of the people of Bahrain, saying, *"Some of them liked Islam, were pleased with it, and embraced it. Others disliked it. Among my people there are Magians and Jews, so command me concerning them"*¹²⁶. So, the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) wrote back to Al-Mundhir:

*"As for what follows: I remind you of Allah, the Almighty and Majestic—for whoever offers sincere advice does so for his own good. Whoever obeys my messengers and follows their command has indeed obeyed me; and whoever is loyal to them has shown loyalty to me. My messengers have praised you highly. I have interceded on your behalf among your people, so leave the Muslims upon what they have accepted of Islam. I have pardoned the sinners among them, so accept them. As long as you act rightly, we will not remove you from your position. Whoever remains upon Judaism or Magianism must pay the jizyah"*¹²⁷. This is how the people of Bahrain entered Islam. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) kept their ruler, Al-Mundhir ibn Sawa, governing them on his behalf, while Al-'Alaa ibn Al-Hadrami remained alongside him as a judge, teacher, and collector of Zakat.

Al-Mundhir ibn Sawa, he was the son of Al-Akhnas, from the tribe of Banu 'Abd al-Qays. There is some scholarly disagreement about whether he personally visited the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him). Some sources affirm that he did, while others argue that he did not meet the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) in person. The renowned scholar Al-Hafidh Ibn Hajar supported this latter view, saying, *"He was not part of the delegation, rather he sent a letter with them declaring his Islam"*¹²⁸. Al-Mundhir passed away shortly after the death of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), in the year 11 AH / 633 CE. His death occurred just before the apostasy (ridda) of some people in Bahrain, which took place at the beginning of Abu Bakr Al-Siddiq's caliphate.

6. THE PROVINCE OF OMAN

6.1. Geographical Location

Oman is located in the southeastern corner of the Arabian Peninsula, situated along the southeastern coast. It overlooks both the Arabian Sea and the Arabian Gulf.¹²⁹ Oman was known by several names in ancient times before Islam. The prominent names were Majan, Muzun, and Oman, the most famous one¹³⁰. The name "Oman" was mentioned in the Hadiths of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him). One such narration is when the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent a man to a certain Arab tribe, and they insulted and beat him. The man returned to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), who said to him, *"If you had gone to the people of Oman, they would not have insulted you or struck you"*¹³¹.

6.2. The Rulers and the Religion of the People of Oman Before Islam

Before the advent of Islam, especially in the period leading up to its arrival, the rulers of Oman belonged to the Azd tribes. This ruling lineage continued until their acceptance of Islam. At the time Islam reached Oman, it was ruled by Jaifar¹³² and his brother 'Abd, the sons of Al-Julanda bin Al-Mustakbir. They both embraced Islam through the efforts of 'Amr ibn Al-'Aas when the Prophet (peace be upon him) had sent him to the region of Oman. However, there is no evidence that they ever met the Prophet (peace be upon him) in person¹³³. The religious landscape in Oman before Islam included small minorities of Christians and Jews, but the vast majority of the population were idol worshippers, making paganism their dominant religion.

6.3. The Early Connection of the People of Oman with the Prophet (peace be upon him)

The beginnings of the contact of the people of Oman with the Messenger (peace be upon him) went through two phases. The first phase was Individual efforts in converting to Islam. Mazin bin Al-Ghadouba (d. 25 AH / 645 CE) is considered the first person from Oman to embrace Islam. Upon

hearing about the Islamic message, he immediately traveled to meet the Messenger (peace be upon him), taking along his servant Salih bin Al-Mutawakkil. Mazin said, *"I broke the idols and went to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), and I embraced Islam"*¹³⁴. In another instance, Bishr bin Sufyan Al-Atki Al-Azdi¹³⁵ from the Azd tribe of Oman came to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) during the year of Al-Hudaybiyyah (6 AH) as a Muslim¹³⁶. This highlights that Islam reached the people of Oman early, just like it did in other regions of the Arabian Peninsula. The people of Yemen and Bahrain embraced Islam before the official propagation reached their lands. The second phase involved correspondence between the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) and the People of Oman. Abu Shaddad Al-Dhimari, one of the people of Oman¹³⁷, mentioned that a letter from the Prophet (peace be upon him) reached them, written on a piece of leather, inviting the people of Oman to Islam. However, he did not specify who delivered the letter nor did he mention the reaction of the people of Oman to it at that time¹³⁸. The ruling leader of Oman who was contemporary to the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) was Jaifar bin Al-Julanda. Al-Baladhuri¹³⁹ mentioned that the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) sent Abu Zayd Al-Ansari to Jaifar bin Al-Julanda in the year 8 AH, carrying a letter inviting him and his people to Islam. The narration suggests that Abu Zayd's mission was more educational and developmental in nature. This also implies that his mission came after the official acceptance of Islam by the people of Oman through the efforts of 'Amr ibn Al-'Aas.

The famous letter that led to the people of Oman accepting Islam was carried by 'Amr ibn al-'Aas (d. 43 AH / 664 CE) in the eighth year of Hijrah¹⁴⁰. Here's the text of the letter:

*"In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful. From Muhammad, the son of 'Abdullah, to Jaifar and 'Abbaad, the sons of al-Julanda. Peace be upon those who follow guidance. As for what follows: I call you both with the call of Islam. Embrace Islam and you both will be safe. I am the Messenger of Allah sent to all people, to warn the living and to establish proof against the disbelievers. If you both accept Islam, I shall appoint you both as rulers over your land. If both of you refuse, then your kingdom will be taken from you. My cavalry will camp in your territory, and my prophethood shall prevail over your rule"*¹⁴¹.

'Amr ibn al-'Aas (may Allah be pleased with him) delivered the Prophet's (peace be upon him) letter to the two brothers, Jaifar and 'Abbaad, and was successful in convincing them of the truth of Islam and its noble human values and civilization. They both embraced Islam, and their people followed them in doing so. The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) confirmed them as rulers over their territory. 'Amr ibn al-'Aas (may Allah be pleased with him) remained there for a while to collect Zakat, provide rulings and judge among people. He praised the two rulers by saying, *"They both believed the Prophet (peace be upon him), gave me full authority over zakat and judgment among their people, and they were both a great help against those who opposed me"*¹⁴². This marked the voluntary entry of the people of Oman into Islam shortly after the Conquest of al-Makkah in the 8th year of Hijrah, much like many other Arab tribes of the Arabian Peninsula.

7. CONCLUSION AND KEY FINDINGS

The research has arrived at important conclusions related to the geographical expansion of the Islamic state during the Prophetic era, the influencing factors behind this expansion, the criteria used for selecting governors, and the administrative approach used to manage these provinces. The most significant findings can be summarized as follows:

Firstly: The Symbolic Status of al-Makkah and Its People Among the Inhabitants of the Arabian Peninsula. The people of the Arabian Peninsula initially rejected Islam when the elite of al-Makkah rejected it. The Prophet (peace be upon him) used to present himself and his message to the Arab tribes during the pilgrimage seasons and at commercial markets, and he even traveled to al-Taa'if, but

not everyone responded positively to his call, and they refused to offer him protection. However, when the people of al-Makkah embraced Islam and accepted the message, all the Arab tribes began coming forward, declaring their acceptance of Islam. That year became known as "The Year of Delegations" ('Am al-Wufud).

Secondly: In the Field of Administration, the research has identified a set of civilizational and administrative values established by the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) in the realm of governance and leadership. Among these values are:

1. Not appointing individuals who seek positions of authority, out of concern that their motivation may be to use the position for material or social gain. The Prophet (peace be upon him) said: *"By Allah, we do not appoint to this work anyone who asks for it..."*
2. Administration in the Spirit of Teamwork. The Prophet (may peace be upon him) advised his appointed officials to cooperate with one another, thus steering administration away from "individualism and ego-driven leadership". The aim for all was unified, to succeed in the tasks entrusted to them. He (may peace be upon him) said: *"Work together in harmony and do not differ."*
3. Making things easy for the People. Among the key administrative values established by the Messenger of Allah (may peace be upon him) was the principle of easing matters for the people, using a pleasant approach when dealing with them, and kindness in dealing with all public affairs. The guidance of the Messenger of Allah (may peace be upon him): *"Give glad tidings and do not repel people; make things easy and do not make them difficult."* And *"Whenever there is gentleness in anything it beautifies it, and whenever it is not removed from anything it makes it defective."*
4. The value of dealing with people and respecting their Privacy. The Prophet (may peace be upon him) used to prepare his governors both culturally and psychologically for the environments they would be working in. For example, he (may peace be upon him) said (to Mu'adh ibn Jabal), *"You are going to a people of the Book (i.e., Jews and Christians)."* And to 'Attab, he said, *"I have appointed you over the people of Allah..."*
5. Interviewing nominated candidate and evaluating the extent of his eligibility for the position. The Prophet (may peace be upon him) would personally assess those being considered for administrative roles, ensuring they possessed the necessary intellectual and cultural competence, especially in handling new or unprecedented issues where there was no clear text or previous ruling to follow. (This is reflected in the famous dialogue when the Prophet asked Mu'adh ibn Jabal how he would judge if a matter arose. Mu'adh replied, *"...I will exert my opinion (ijtihad) and do my best."*

Supervising his appointed officials and removing them from their positions if the public interest demanded it, especially in cases where people submitted complaints against a governor or administrator. Failing to address such concerns could lead to inherent frustration among the populace and potentially cause tension or alienation between the official and the community in their work environment.

6. Flexibility in appointing officials, taking into consideration the specific needs of each region and the state's broader political strategy to gain new alliances. The Prophet (peace be upon him) appointed 'Attab ibn Asid to break the monopoly of Quraysh elites over leadership. He chose (peace be upon him) 'Uthmān ibn Abi al-'Aaṣ for al-Taa'if because the people there needed someone deeply committed to learning the religion and teaching it to others. The appointments like Baadhaan, al-Mundhir ibn Sawa, and Jaifar ibn al-Julanda were made based on the state's need to expand and maintain regional stability.

7. Winning Hearts (Ta'lif al-Qulub). The Prophet (peace be upon him) employed this strategy as one of the most effective methods, especially with tribal leaders and rulers. A clear example of are the letters he sent to the rulers of Bahrain, Oman, and the Persian governor of Yemen, in which he assured them that whoever accepted Islam and pledged loyalty to the Islamic state would be allowed to retain their leadership. Some of the leaders and rulers responded positively to the Prophet's (peace be upon him) call, embraced Islam, and he (peace be upon him) retained them in their leadership positions and responsibilities.

Thirdly: The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) established salaries for governors, as indicated by historical sources regarding the salary of 'Attab ibn Asid, the governor of al-Makkah. His wage is considered the first recorded regular salary received by an official in the newly founded Islamic state.

Fourthly: During the Prophetic era, the Islamic state was composed of six provinces, including the capital, all of which entered Islam willingly and without warfare.

Footnote

- 1) Ibn Abd al-Barr, Abu Umar al-Namri al-Qurtubi (d. 463 AH / 1071 CE), *Al-Tamhid lima fi al-Muwatta min al-Asanid*, Vol. 17, edited and annotated by Bashar Awwad Ma'ruf and others, Al-Furqan Islamic Heritage Foundation – London, 1st edition, 1439 AH, Vol. 15, p. 101.
- 2) Qur'an, Surah Al-Ahzab, Verse 13.
- 3) Al-Hamawi, Shihab al-Din Abu Abd Allah Yaqut ibn Abd Allah al-Rumi al-Hamawi (d. 626 AH / 1225 CE), *Mu'jam al-Buldan*, Vol. 7, Dar Sader, Beirut, 2nd edition, 1995 CE, Vol. 5, p. 430.
- 4) Surah Al-Hashr: 9
- 5) Abu Ubayd Abdullah bin Abdul Aziz bin Muhammad Al-Bakri Al-Andalusi (d. 487 AH / 1094 CE) – *Mu'jam Ma'ista'jam min Asma' al-Bilad wal-Mawadi'*, Vol. 4, Alam Al-Kutub, Beirut, 3rd Edition, 1403 AH, Vol. 4, p. 1201.
- 6) Al-Bakri. *Al-Masalik wa Al-Mamalik*, Vol. 1, p. 413.
- 7) Al-Ya'qubi. *Tarikh Al-Ya'qubi*, Vol. 1, p. 215.
- 8) Abu Al-Fida, Ismail bin Kathir (774 AH / 1373 CE). *Al-Sirah Al-Nabawiyyah*, Vol. 4, edited by Mustafa Abdul Wahid, Issa Al-Babi Al-Halabi, Cairo, 1395 AH - 1976 CE, Vol. 2, p. 178.
- 9) Banu Amr bin Awf – a branch of the Khazraj tribe.
- 10) Kulthum bin Al-Hadm bin Imri'u' Al-Qais bin Al-Harith bin Zaid bin Malik Al-Awfi Al-Awsi. He was the first from the Ansar to pass away after the Prophet (peace be upon him) arrived in al-Madinah. See: Ibn Hajar, Ahmad bin Ali bin Muhammad bin Ahmad bin Hajar Al-Asqalani (d. 852 AH / 1449 CE), *Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah*, Vol. 8, edited by Adel Ahmed Abdul Mawjood and Ali Muhammad Mu'awwad, Dar Al-Kutub Al-'Ilmiyyah. Beirut: 1st Edition, 1415 AH, Vol. 5, p. 462.
- 11) Safiyu Al-Rahman Al-Mubarakfuri (d. 1427 AH / 2006 CE). *Al-Raheeq Al-Makhtum*. Vol. 1, Dar Al-Salam for Publishing and Distribution. Riyadh: Vol. 1, p. 149.
- 12) Al-Mirbad is the place where dates are dried. Ibn Al-Athir, Majd Al-Din Abu Al-Sa'adat Al-Mubarak bin Muhammad bin Muhammad bin Muhammad bin Abdu al-Karim Al-Shaybani Al-Jazari Ibn Al-Athir (d. 606 AH), *An-Nihayah fi Gharib Al-Hadith wa al-Athar*, Vol. 5, edited by: Tahir Ahmad Al-Zawi - Mahmoud Muhammad Al-Tanahi, Al-Maktabah Al-'Ilmiyyah. Beirut: 1399 AH - 1979 CE, Vol. 2, p. 182.
- 13) Regarding its virtue, the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: "Whoever purifies himself in his house, then comes to the Mosque of Quba and prays in it, he will have the reward of performing an 'Umrah." Ibn Majah, Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Yazid bin Majah Al-Qazwini (d. 273 AH / 886 CE), *Sunan Ibn Majah*, Vol. 5, edited by: Shu'ayb Al-Arna'ut (d. 1438 AH / 2016 CE), Dar Al-Risalah Al-'Alamiyyah, first edition, 1430 AH - 2009 CE, Vol. 2, Hadith No. (1412).

- 14) In this location, a beautiful mosque was recently built, called "Masjid Al-Jum'ah" (Friday Mosque), because it was where the Prophet (peace be upon him) led his first-ever Friday prayer.
- 15) Ibn Sa'd, Muhammad bin Sa'd bin Mani' Al-Hashimi Al-Basri (d. 230 AH / 845 CE). *Al-Tabaqat Al-Kubra*, Vol. 9, edited by Muhammad Abdul Qadir 'Ata, published by: Dar Al-Kutub Al-'Ilmiyyah – Beirut, first edition, 1410 AH - 1990 CE, Vol. 1, p. 183; Ibn Hisham. *Al-Sirah Al-Nabawiyah*, Vol. 2, p. 273.
- 16) Al-Bukhari, Muhammad bin Ismail (d. 256 AH / 870 CE), *Al-Jami' As-Sahih Al-Mukhtasar*, Vol. 7, edited by: Dr. Mustafa Dib Al-Bugha, published by: Dar Ibn Kathir, Al-Yamamah – Beirut, third edition, 1407 AH – 1987 CE, Hadith No. (3699).
- 17) Surah Ali 'Imran: 97
- 18) Muhammad bin Abdullah bin Ahmad Al-Azraqi (d. 250 AH / 864 CE), *Akhbar al-Makkah wa ma Jaa Fiha min Al-Athar*, Vol. 2, edited by: Rushdi Al-Salih Malhas, Dar Al-Andalus, Beirut:Vol. 1, p. 34.
- 19) ¹ Surah Al-Baqarah: 127
- 20) Al-Fasi: Muhammad bin Ahmad bin Ali, Taqi Al-Din, Abu Al-Tayyib Al-Makki Al-Hasani Al-Fasi (d. 832 AH / 1429 CE), *Shifa' Al-Gharam Bi-Akhbar Al-Balad Al-Haram*, Vol. 2, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah, first edition, 2000 CE, Vol. 1, p. 126.
- 21) Muhammad bin Ishaq bin Yasar Al-Muttalibi by allegiance, Al-Madani (d. 151 AH / 768 CE), *Sirat Ibn Ishaq*, Vol. 1, edited by: Suhail Zakkar, Dar Al-Fikr: Beirut, Lebanon, first edition, 1978, Vol. 1, p. 109.
- 22) Al-Azraqi, Muhammad bin Abdullah (d. 250 AH / 854 CE), *In his book Akhbar Makkah wa ma Jaa Fiha min Al-Athar*; edited by: Rushdi Malhas, Vol. 1, 8th edition, Makkah Al-Mukarramah: Matabi' Dar Al-Thaqafah, 1996 CE. Al-Ansari, Muhammad, *Al-Makkah Al-Mukarramah and the Architecture of Al-Masjid Al-Haram*, in *Al-Hayat* (Newspaper), Issue No. 13452, January 2000 CE.
- 23) Surah Al-Fath: 24
- 24) Surah Aal-e-Imran: 96
- 25) Surah At-Tin: 3
- 26) Surah Al-An'am: 92
- 27) Surah Al-Qasas: 85
- 28) Surah Al-Isra: 1
- 29) Surah Al-Hajj: 29
- 30) Yaqut Al-Hamawi, *Mu'jam Al-Buldan*, Vol. 4, p. 225.
- 31) Al-Bayhaqi, *Dala'il Al-Nubuwwah*, Vol. 1, p. 93.
- 32) Al-Qurtubi, Abu Abdullah, Muhammad bin Ahmad Al-Ansari Al-Qurtubi (671 AH / 1273 CE), *Al-Jami' Li Ahkam Al-Qur'an*, 20 vols., edited by: Ahmad Al-Bardouni and Ibrahim Atfayesh, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Misriyyah – Cairo, 2nd edition, 1384 AH - 1964 CE, Vol. 11, p. 115.
- 33) Surah Maryam: 54
- 34) Ibn Hisham, *Al-Seerah Al-Nabawiyah*, Vol. 1, p. 72.
- 35) The leader of the hypocrites used to outwardly profess Islam while inwardly concealing disbelief. He had followers, whose characteristics were exposed by the Holy Qur'an, especially in Surah At-Tawbah, which is also called "Al-Fadihah" (the exposer), as it revealed the reality of the hypocrites.
- 36) Al-Albani, *Sahih Sunan Abi Dawood*, Hadith No. (3004).
- 37) Ibn Sa'd, Muhammad bin Sa'd bin Mani' Al-Hashemi Al-Basri (d. 230 AH / 845 CE), *Al-Tabaqat Al-Kubra*, 9 vols., edited by: Muhammad Abdul Qadir Atta, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah – Beirut, 1st edition, 1410 AH - 1990 CE, Vol. 6, p. 5 (6/5). Abu 'Umar, Yusuf bin Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdul Barr (d. 463 AH / 1071

- CE), *Al-Isti'ab fi Ma'rifat Al-Ashab*, 4 vols., edited by: Ali Muhammad Al-Bajawi (d. 1399 AH), Maktabat Nahdat Misr – Cairo, 1380 AH - 1960 CE, Vol. 3, p. 1024. 'Izz Al-Din Abu Al-Hasan Ali bin Muhammad bin Abdul Karim Al-Jazari, known as Ibn Al-Athir (d. 630 AH), *Usd Al-Ghabah fi Ma'rifat Al-Sahabah*, 7 vols., Egyptian Knowledge Association, printed at: Al-Wahbiyyah Press – Cairo, 1285 - 1286 AH, Vol. 3, p. 358. Ibn Hajar, *Al-Isabah*, Vol. 4, p. 357.
- 38) He embraced Islam and his faith became strong. He passed away in the year 40 AH in Damascus.
- 39) Muhammad bin Sa'd bin Mani' Al-Hashimi Al-Basri, known as Ibn Sa'd, *Al-Tabaqat Al-Kubra*, edited by Muhammad Abdul Qadir Ata, published by Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah – Beirut, first edition, 1410 AH - 1990 CE, (Vol. 2, p. 104).
- 40) Ibn Hisham, *Al-Sirah* (Vol. 2, p. 500).
- 41) Ibn Hajar Al-Asqalani, *Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah* (Vol. 6, p. 415).
- 42) Al-Waaqidi, *Al-Maghazi* (Vol. 3, p. 889).
- 43) Abu Muhammad Ali bin Ahmad bin Sa'id bin Hazm Al-Andalusi Al-Qurtubi Al-Zahiri (d. 456 AH), *Jawami' Al-Sirah Al-Nabawiyyah*, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah – Beirut, (p. 198).
- 44) Al-Waaqidi, *Al-Maghazi* (Vol. 3, p. 959).
- 45) Ibn Hajar, *Al-Isabah* (Vol. 6, p. 81).
- 46) Ibn Sa'd, *Al-Tabaqat* (Vol. 6, p. 5).
- 47) Al-Waaqidi, *Al-Maghazi* (Vol. 3, p. 959).
- 48) *Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah* (Vol. 5, p. 116).
- 49) Ibn Abdul Barr, *Al-Isti'ab* (Vol. 3, p. 1024).
- 50) *Al-Isti'ab* (Vol. 3, p. 1024).
- 51) Muhammad bin Muhammad Hasan Shurrab, *Al-Ma'alim Al-Atheerah fi Al-Sunnah wal-Sirah*, Dar Al-Qalam, Al-Dar Al-Shamiyyah - Damascus-Beirut, first edition, 1411 AH (p. 170).
- 52) Shihab al-Din Abu Abdullah Yaqut bin Abdullah Al-Rumi Al-Hamawi (d. 626 AH), *Mu'jam Al-Buldan*, Dar Sader, Beirut, second edition, 1995 CE (Vol. 4, p. 9).
- 53) Muhammad Shurrab, *Al-Ma'alim Al-Atheerah* (p. 295).
- 54) Abu Abdullah Ahmad bin Muhammad bin Ishaq Al-Hamdani, known as Ibn Al-Faqih (d. 365 AH), *Al-Buldan*, edited by Yusuf Al-Hadi, published by Alam Al-Kutub, Beirut, first edition, 1416 AH - 1996 CE (p. 79).
- 55) Surah Al-Zukhruf: 31 – The two men mentioned, according to some scholars, refer to Utbah ibn Rabi'ah from al-Makkah and Habib ibn Amr Al-Thaqafi from al-Taa'if.
- 56) Abu Ja'far Muhammad ibn Jarir Al-Tabari (224–310 AH), *Jami' Al-Bayan 'an Ta'wil Ay Al-Qur'an*, edited by Dr. Abdullah bin Abdul Mohsin Al-Turki, Dar Hajr for Printing, Publishing, and Distribution, Cairo, Egypt, first edition, 1422 AH - 2001 CE (Vol. 20, p. 581).
- 57) See: Sa'id bin Muhammad bin Ahmad Al-Afghani (d. 1417 AH), *Aswaq Al-Arab fi Al-Jahiliyyah wal-Islam*, p. 97.
- 58) The Souq of 'Ukaz operated from the beginning of Dhul-Qa'dah for twenty days, followed by the Souq of Majannah for ten days, and then the Souq of Dhu Al-Majaz started at the beginning of Dhul-Hijjah. – Abu Ubaid Abdullah bin Abdul Aziz bin Muhammad Al-Bakri Al-Andalusi (d. 487 AH), *Mu'jam Ma Istajam min Asma' Al-Bilad wa al-Mawadi'*, published by Alam Al-Kutub, Beirut, third edition, 1403 AH (Vol. 3, p. 959).
- 59) Al-Bayhaqi, *Dala'il Al-Nubuwwah* (Vol. 2, p. 101).

- 60) Abu Al-Mundhir Hisham bin Muhammad Abu Al-Nadr Ibn Al-Sa'ib Ibn Bishr Al-Kalbi (d. 204 AH), *Kitab Al-Asnam*, edited by Ahmad Zaki Pasha, published by Dar Al-Kutub Al-Masriyah – Cairo, fourth edition, 2000 CE (p. 17).
- 61) Ibn Al-Kalbi, *Kitab Al-Asnam* (p. 18).
- 62) Hunayn: A valley located between Mecca and Ta'if, where the well-known Battle of Hunayn took place on the 14th of Shawwal in the 8th year of Hijrah. The leader of the polytheists was Malik ibn 'Awf Al-Nasri from the Hawazin tribe. Allah Almighty mentioned the Battle of Hunayn in the Qur'an: {Certainly, Allah helped you in many battlefields and on the day of Hunayn, when you were proud of your great numbers, but they availed you nothing; the earth, vast as it was, became constrained for you, then you turned your backs in retreat.} (*Surah At-Tawbah: 25*)
- 63) Manjaniq (Catapult): A siege weapon used to launch projectiles without gunpowder to destroy fortifications.
- 64) Dabbabah: A protective structure made from cowhide, used to shield soldiers from enemy arrows.
- 65) Al-Hamawi, *Mu'jam Al-Buldan* (4/12).
- 66) Al-Waaqidi, *Al-Maghazi* (p. 931).
- 67) Previous reference (p. 937).
- 68) Al-Dhahabi, *Siyar A'lam Al-Nubala* (2/258).
- 69) Muhammad bin Umar bin Waqid Al-Sahmi Al-Aslami Al-Madani, Abu Abdullah, Al-Waaqidi (d. 207 AH), *Al-Maghazi*, edited by Marsden Jones, published by Dar Al-A'lamy – Beirut, third edition, 1409 AH / 1989 CE (3/968).
- 70) Abu Nu'aym mentioned in his book *Ma'rifat Al-Sahaba* that 'Uthman ibn Abi Al-'Aas accepted Islam at the age of twenty-seven.
- 71) Muhammad ibn Sa'd, *Al-Tabaqat Al-Kubra* (8/68); Ibn 'Abd Al-Barr, *Al-Isti'ab* (3/1035); Ibn Al-Athir, *Usud Al-Ghabah* (3/574); Ibn Hajar, *Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah* (4/373).
- 72) Shams al-Din Muhammad ibn Ahmad ibn Uthman Al-Dhahabi (d. 748 AH), *Siyar A'lam Al-Nubala*, edited by Shu'ayb Al-Arna'ut and others, published by Mu'assasat Al-Risalah, third edition: 1405 AH (2/374).
- 73) Muhammad ibn Umar ibn Waqid Al-Sahmi Al-Aslami Al-Madani, Abu 'Abdullah Al-Waaqidi (d. 207 AH), *Al-Maghazi*, edited by Marsden Jones, published by Dar Al-A'lamy – Beirut, third edition, 1409 AH / 1989 CE (3/968).
- 74) Ibn Hajar, *Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah* (4/374). A similar stance was taken by Suhayl ibn 'Amr with the people of al-Makkah.
- 75) Muhammad ibn Sa'd ibn Mani' Al-Hashimi Al-Basri, known as Ibn Sa'd, *Al-Tabaqat Al-Kubra*, study and verification by Muhammad 'Abd Al-Qadir 'Ata, Dar Al-Kutub Al-'Ilmiyyah – Beirut, first edition, 1410 AH - 1990 CE (6/48).
- 76) Muhammad ibn Yusuf Al-Salihi Al-Shami (d. 942 AH).
- 77) Muhammad ibn Sa'd, *Al-Tabaqat* (6/48); *Subul Al-Huda wa Al-Rashad fi Sirat Khayr Al-'Ibad*, which discusses the Prophet's virtues, signs of his prophethood, actions, and conditions from beginning to end, verified by Sheikh 'Adil Ahmad 'Abd Al-Mawjud and Sheikh 'Ali Muhammad Mu'awwad, published by Dar Al-Kutub Al-'Ilmiyyah, Beirut – Lebanon, first edition, 1414 AH - 1993 CE (6/299).
- 78) Yemen: Pronounced with vowelization, it was named so according to Ibn 'Abbas because it is on the right side of the Ka'bah. Perhaps he meant that it appears to be on the right for those approaching the Ka'bah from the west. See: Yaqut Al-Hamawi, *Mu'jam Al-Buldan* (5/447).
- 79) Yaqut Al-Hamawi, *Mu'jam Al-Buldan* (5/447).

- 80) Ibid.
- 81) Yaqut Al-Hamawi, Mu'jam Al-Buldan (5/445).
- 82) Surah Saba: 15.
- 83) Surah Al-Naml: 44.
- 84) Jawad Ali (1993), Al-Mufassal fi Tarikh Al-'Arab Qabl Al-Islam (Second Edition), Beirut, Lebanon: Beirut (1/135).
- 85) Ibid. (1/115).
- 86) Surah Al-Hijr: 94.
- 87) The enumeration of names is derived from the Yemeni Fatwa Gate available at: <https://www.fatwagate.com/ar/category/%D9%81%D8%AA%D8%A7%D9%88%D9%89>.
- 88) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (2/494).
- 89) Ibn Hisham, Al-Sirah (1/180).
- 90) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (5/377).
- 91) Ibn Abd Al-Barr, Al-Isti'ab (2/464).
- 92) Ibn Abd Al-Barr, Al-Isti'ab (4/1762); Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (4/181).
- 93) Ibn Hisham, Al-Sirah Al-Nabawiyah (4/797).
- 94) Ibid. (4/798).
- 95) Ibn Hajar mentioned him in the third section of Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah, listing those who lived during the Prophet ﷺ's time, embraced Islam, but did not attain the honor of companionship. Abu Al-Fadl Ahmad ibn Ali ibn Muhammad ibn Hajar Al-Asqalani (d. 852 AH), Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz Al-Sahabah, edited by Adel Ahmad Abdul Mawjoud and Ali Muhammad Mu'awwad, published by Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyyah – Beirut, first edition, 1415 AH (1/664).
- 96) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (1/465).
- 97) Abd al-Malik ibn Hisham ibn Ayyub al-Himyari al-Ma'afiri, Abu Muhammad, Jamal al-Din (d. 213 AH), Al-Sirah al-Nabawiyah (The Prophetic Biography) by Ibn Hisham, edited by Taha Abd al-Raouf, published by United Technical Printing Company (1/61).
- 98) Abu Nu'aym Ahmad ibn Abdullah ibn Ahmad ibn Ishaq ibn Musa ibn Mehran al-Asbahani (d. 430 AH), Dala'il al-Nubuwwah (Proofs of Prophethood), edited by Dr. Muhammad Rawas Qalaji and Abdul Barr Abbas, published by Dar al-Nafa'is, Beirut, 2nd edition, 1406 AH - 1986 CE (p. 348).
- 99) Muhammad ibn Sa'd, Al-Tabaqat (The Major Classes), (5/533).
- 100) Abu Ja'far Muhammad ibn Jarir al-Tabari (224 - 310 AH), Tarikh al-Tabari = History of Prophets and Kings, edited by Muhammad Abu al-Fadl Ibrahim [d. 1401 AH], published by Dar al-Ma'arif in Egypt, 2nd edition, 1387 AH - 1967 CE (3/158).
- 101) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (1/664).
- 102) Al-Aswad al-Ansi claimed prophethood and spread corruption in Yemen. He was killed by Fayruz, who regretted his collaboration with al-Aswad. When he was informed of the Prophet's ﷺ call to eliminate al-Aswad, he was delighted, seeing it as an opportunity to atone for his cooperation with him and to take revenge for the humiliation he had suffered. Fayruz contacted Azad, the wife of Badhan, whom al-Aswad had killed and taken for himself. She resented al-Aswad and, together with Fayruz, Dadhawayh, and Qays, facilitated their entry into al-Aswad's palace, allowing them to kill him. Muhammad Rida (d. 1369 AH), Abu Bakr al-Siddiq: The First of the Rightly Guided Caliphs, published by Dar Ihya' al-Kutub al-'Arabiyyah, 2nd edition, 1369 AH - 1950 CE (p. 45).
- 103) Khair al-Din bin Mahmoud bin Muhammad bin Ali bin Faris al-Zirkili al-Dimashqi (d. 1396 AH), Al-'I'lam (The Notables), published by Dar al-'Ilm lil-Malayin, 15th edition - May 2002 (7/258).
- 104) Ibn Sa'd, Al-Tabaqat (3/583-590). Al-Dhahabi, Siyar A'lam al-Nubala' (3/296).

- 105) The city of al-Jund is located near Taiz, and it contains Masjid al-Jund, which was established by Mu'adh ibn Jabal, may Allah be pleased with him. Al-Hamawi, Shihab al-Din Abu 'Abdullah Yaqut ibn 'Abdullah al-Rumi al-Hamawi (d. 626 AH), Mu'jam al-Buldan (Dictionary of Countries), published by Dar Sader, Beirut, 2nd edition, 1995 CE (2/169).
- 106) Al-Mikhlaf: The term for region in the language of the people of Yemen.
- 107) Sahih al-Bukhari, Hadith number: (4341).
- 108) Himyar: A Qahtani tribe and one of the largest tribes in the Arabian Peninsula, with extensions in most Arab countries.
- 109) Al-Bayhaqi, Dalail al-Nubuwwah (5/404).
- 110) Ibn al-Qayyim, Zad al-Ma'ad fi Hadi Khayr al-'Ibad (2/9).
- 111) Hussain ibn Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Diyar Bakri (d. 966 AH), Tārikh al-Khamis fi Ahwal Anfās al-Nafis, published by Dar Sader, Beirut, Lebanon (2/143).
- 112) 'Amwas: A village in Palestine located several miles from Jerusalem, famous for the plague that began there during the caliphate of 'Umar ibn al-Khattab, may Allah be pleased with him. More than thirty thousand, mostly companions of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him), were martyred because of it.
- 113) Ibn Abdul Barr, Al-Isti'ab fi Ma'rifat al-Ashab (4/1762).
- 114) The Ash'ari Tribe: A well-known tribe among the people of Yemen. It is said that they were named after their ancestor, who was born with hair all over his body.
- 115) One of the social customs of the Arabs before Islam was that when a man left his tribe for any reason and wanted to settle in another place, he had to form an alliance with a powerful person who could protect and defend him.
- 116) Ibn Hisham, Al-Sirah al-Nabawiyah.
- 117) Ibn Abdul Barr, Al-Isti'ab fi Ma'rifat al-Ashab (4/1762).
- 118) Ibn al-Qayyim, Zad al-Ma'ad fi Hadi Khayr al-'Ibad (1/474).
- 119) Aziz al-Din Ibn al-Athir, Abu al-Hasan Ali ibn Muhammad al-Jazari (d. 630 AH), Asad al-Ghaba fi Ma'rifat al-Sahabah, edited by Ali Muhammad Muawad & Adel Ahmed Abd al-Mawgood, published by Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyyah, Beirut, Lebanon, first edition, 1415 AH - 1994 CE (3/364).
- 120) Sahih al-Bukhari, Hadith number: (1559). Sahih Muslim, Hadith number: (1221).
- 121) Ibn Abdul Barr, Al-Isti'ab fi Ma'rifat al-Ashab (4/1764). Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah fi Tamyiz al-Sahabah (4/183).
- 122) Jawaad Ali, Al-Mufassal fi Tarikh al-'Arab (2/212 - 3/19).
- 123) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (3/471). Ibn al-Athir, Asad al-Ghaba (5/225).
- 124) Ibn Sa'd, Al-Tabaqat (1/226).
- 125) Ibn al-Athir, Asad al-Ghaba (5/255).
- 126) Ibn Hazm, Jawami' al-Sirah (p. 232).
- 127) Ibn Sayyid al-Nas, Uyun al-Athar (2/352).
- 128) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (6/170).
- 129) Al-Ani, Abdul Rahman, Tarikh Oman fi al-'Aswar al-Islamiyyah al-Oula, Dar al-Hikma, London (p. 37).
- 130) Jawaad Ali, Al-Mufassal (2: 208 – 7: 202).
- 131) Muslim, Sahih Muslim, Hadith number: (2544).
- 132) We could not find the date of his death.
- 133) Ibn Abdul Barr, Al-Istihab (2/173).
- 134) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah in Tamyiz al-Sahabah (5/520).

- 135) We could not find the date of his death.
- 136) Ibn Hajar, Al-Isabah (1/429).
- 137) He was mentioned by Al-Suyuti in "Who Lived 120 Years Among the Companions." See: Jalal al-Din Abd al-Rahman al-Suyuti (d. 911 AH), Rih al-Nasreen Fi Man Ashaa Min Al-Sahaba Mi'atayn Wa 'Ishrin (The Winds of the Roses on Those Among the Companions Who Lived 120 Years), edited by Adnan Ahmad Majood. Dar Al-Wafa for Publishing and Distribution, Jeddah, 1985. (p. 65).
- 138) Ibn al-Athir, Asad al-Ghabah (6/159).
- 139) Al-Baladhuri, Futuh al-Buldan (p. 83).
- 140) Ibn Saad, Al-Tabaqat (1/226).
- 141) Ibn Tulun, (1987, p. 97).
- 142) Ibn Sayyid al-Nas, Uyoun al-Athar (1993, Vol. 2, p. 337).

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